

The African Growth and Opportunity Act and Marketing Implications for Nigeria

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Ezekiel, Maurice Sunday**-Department of Marketing-University of Calabar-Calabar, Cross River State.P.M.B.1115, Nigeria. ⁽²⁾**Mr.Kajang Joshua Lane**-Department of Marketing-Faculty of Management Sciences-University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria ⁽³⁾**Dr. Ehikwe Andrew Egede**-Department of Marketing-Faculty of Management Sciences-University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria

Abstract

The topic of study is on Agoa with a specific focus on the implications of marketing for Nigeria. Agoa was a great window for SSA countries to improve their exports to America with a provision to meet the prerequisites of standards and phyto standards of products. A survey of the export markets of agriculture and non-agricultural or non-energy exports from Nigeria to the United States was conducted among various groups, farmers, corporate organizations, export promotion embassies and others responsible for exports. The methodology was to review the extensive literature of the exports conditions for the exports and selected interview of individuals in some of the groups and government agencies responsible for export. The findings showed the gap was greatly influenced by poor quality products, non-production of the right products, lack of capacity and capability to produce the right products, zero percent or less than one percent was achieved, no utilization of marketing principles and practices, product grading, good packaging, little or no value added to raw products, poor market information (marketer and consumer) research, and weak or poor entry strategy to US market. Nigeria should adopt the marketing practices of entry strategy using available intermediaries in US market, collaboration with customers in US market, proper product package, preparation etc.

Keywords: AGOA, product standardization, marketing information need, processing storage, marketing communication and integrated agricultural production system.

1.0 Introduction

The introduction of the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in May 2000, after it was signed into law by President Bill Clinton of the United States of America was to serve as a gateway to improved export of products particularly in agriculture from Nigeria and other countries in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) to the United States of America. The extant literature prior to this time had recorded the existing relationship as rather frosty, (Schneidman and Lewis, 2012). The focus of AGOA was to encourage the economic growth of Nigeria and other Sub Saharan Africa countries through export leverage in the reduction of tariffs and non-tariff barriers as an incentive critical and capable of fostering intra-regional integration of SSA and other trade relations with the United States of America. The lacuna in this expectation of export leverage is the question of Nigeria being able to meet the output and quality standards, the capacity for export and the requirements for both primary and secondary products for US markets, (Akanji, 2007). This thinking exacerbate the changes to AGOA terms from AGOA I to II, III and IV all directed at expansion of the eligible lists of products and the improvements in the sanitary and phytosanitary standards in order to meet U.S market requirements and the limitation of AGOA privileges and tenor to 2015 (TDA, 2000, Schneidman and Lewis, 2012). The SSA countries had a low standard of processing, packaging, transportation and other physical distribution requirements that needed improvement to enhance the value of both primary produce and secondary products export that would meet the expectations of the end users in US markets.

Nigeria is recognized by the U.S market (USDCITA, 2012), with an import potential of about 47.7%, albeit predominantly energy product. The agriculture and manufacturing including leather products are the sectors with the greatest export potential (USITC, 2005) and a possible source for future diversification of the economy with trade liberalization in the opening of the US market. Trade remains a major option for Africa industrial development (Thompson 2004, President George W. Bush, 2003) with wider product appeal according to consumer preferences in the global market particularly the United States that provides the open market for the home products. AGOA is expected to encourage general improvements in social and profit oriented marketing (Akunji, 2007b).

The core marketing challenges to the optimization of the AGOA opportunities are the technical training and capacity building, market research and information management and improved production process. The essence is to guarantee quality to meet the sanitary and phytosanitary standards especially in the processing of the agricultural produce to finished or semi-finished products as major determinants on the final value of the products at both local and the foreign markets. The storage and packaging facilities are also strategic as key marketing infrastructure that ought to deliver safer and quality products to the United States market at minimum transactional costs to the country of export. The absence of market intelligence gathering on product and price information in Nigeria and the U.S markets inhibits AGOA opportunities including consumer's preferences for agricultural products that are produced throughout the year. This paper is focused on evaluating the implementation of Africa Growth and Opportunity Act and the marketing implications for Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The access to U.S markets through the removal of trade barriers under AGOA could pose greater challenges to the economies of SSA countries, (Akanj, 2007c). The various thoughts on AGOA are however, mixed with different expectations as some believe that it has opened the window of opportunities in the relationship that engages the US and the SSA countries to friendly policies of greater cooperation and the boosting of trade relations for a more integrated SSA economics, while others feared that the constraints on the eligibility requirements of the act are unfair to sub-Saharan African countries. There are doubts that AGOA has any positive impact on apparel exports from a small number of SSA countries but no evidence of AGOA induced gain in any other sector, though, the report also held in contradiction that exports from SSA to the United States have significantly increased since 2000 with a large share of the exports using AGOA preference while small amount of the exports can be linked directly to AGOA, (Ondon and Mathew 2011). In another study, Noure and Staatz (2003) report that data on the impact of AGOA on agricultural export was not statistically different from zero. Agriculture has not played a central role in the accomplishment of AGOA, with a contribution of less than 1% of AGOA exports. There is a general lack of value added in agricultural products in Africa and Nigeria in particular (Schneidan and Leins, 2012). A recent report indicated that AGOA agricultural benefits are constrained by the same problems that existed before the AGOA act and by the exclusion of some agricultural products from AGOA list (Kimberlie and Wallace, 2004). There is an apparent gap under the AGOA act of 2000 between the energy sector and other sectors that include textile and apparel export to the United States market and the agricultural sector that has the largest potential to contribute to the national economies of sub-Saharan Africa. Nigeria is one of the five top beneficiaries of AGOA though relatively energy drove, but not listed in the ten leading exporting countries on agriculture and apparel products under AGOA (USITCT D, 2011; Akanji, 2007).

This study particularly questions the bases on how to fill the gap in the contributions of marketing to the optimization of AGOA benefits to Nigeria, considering the difficulties in the standardization of various agricultural products to meet the sanitary and phytosanitary standards required by the U.S market and the threat posed by the apparent inability of Nigeria to realize the export capacity optimization? The fundamental problems with Nigeria participation in AGOA on minimal capacity and the ability for the processing and packaging of acceptable products, organized marketing information system on the changing demands or preferences of the U.S market and the entire physical distribution processes under taken by small and big farm product exporters constitute a great dilemma. The crux of marketing implications on how acceptable products could be made available to fill the gap of non-energy export to the US market and thereby, maximize the quota in Nigerian export opportunity under AGOA as enjoyed by other SSA countries constitute the nexus of this study.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- (i).To examine standardization of agricultural products for enhanced export capacity optimization of Nigeria under AGOA
- (ii).To examine the impact of processing and packaging of agricultural products to the optimization of export by farmers in Nigeria under AGOA

(iii).To examine the marketing information needs required to maximize the capacity of agricultural products export of Nigeria under AGOA

(iv).Toexamine the effect of agricultural production under the integrated farming system as a means of capacity optimization of export products of Nigeria under AGOA.

(v).To evaluate the marketing communication strategy adopted by Nigeria under AGOA.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions that follow are:

- (i) What is the standard of agricultural products required for Nigeria to optimize the capacity of export under AGOA?
- (ii) Is there any significant impact of processing and packaging of agricultural products for optimization of export in Nigeria under AGOA?
- (iii) What is the marketing information required for maximizing the export capacity of agricultural products in Nigeria under AGOA?
- (iv) What are the effects of agricultural production under the integrated farming system as a means for export capacity optimization of Nigeria under AGOA?
- (v) What is the marketing communication strategies adopted for export optimization by Nigeria under AGOA?

1.5 Theoretical Framework

International trade has existed over the years on the basis of mutual interests and comparative advantage between the countries entering into trade relations, but the leverage of sponsorship of some countries by another for the purpose of encouraging economic growth through waiver of trade barriers such as quota, tariffs and taxes on export as obtained in AGOA is a challenging development in modern concept of trade relations. The economic rationality of the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) promoted by the United States of America for all the countries in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) has remained a model and a redefinition of trade relations in the modern world. The tenets of AGOA may be politically motivated but its economic objectives are directed towards encouraging the countries involved to improve their export drive.

The conditions for eligibility of countries for participation in AGOA are “ Market based economies, rule of law, political pluralism, elimination of barriers to USA trade and investment, protection of intellectual property, efforts to combat corruption, policies to reduce poverty, increasing availability of health care and educational opportunities, protection of human rights and worker rights, elimination of child labour practices, not to undermine US security or support terrorism,” (www.trade.gov/agoa/eligibility/index.asp). The Generalised System of Preferences (GSP) established by the UNCTAD in 1968 was completed by the USA in 1974 and culminating in special preference for AGOA initiatives in 2001, (Hoekman et al., 2006a). The essence of the two is “non reciprocal trade preference that provides duty free treatment to US imports of certain products from eligible Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) countries 34 and GSP covering 38 SSA countries and generally to about 120 countries,”(www.fas.org/sgp/crs/row/R43173). AGOA is expected to facilitate the integration of SSA countries into the global economy by providing preferential access to the US markets for exporters from these countries. The Least Developed Countries (LDC) pay zero tariffs on 4650 tariff lines or products and a further 1750 lines {Hoekman et al., 2006b), The provisions made on GSP cover over 4600 items and AGOA allow export of 6400 items including those items of GSP. Though market based economy is reliant on the forces of demand and supply, AGOA is open to SSA countries with the capacity to export products to the USA without restraints albeit meeting consumer requirements for product quality, price, promotion, market information, delivery terms and customer services, preferences and satisfaction.

2.1 Literature Review

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) was mooted under president Clinton of United States of America (USA) in October 2000 by declaring 34 countries of Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) eligible for trade benefits under AGOA and it formed the largest possible number of SSA countries able to take advantages of such a declaration. The conditions then were formative under AGOA 1 (The Trade and Development Act of 2000), and this was improved upon by president Bush in May 2002 when AGOA 11 was signed that expanded preferential access for imports and in 2004 AGOA 111 came to be as the Acceleration Act with a

provision for 3rd country fabric provision for 3 years to 2007 and AGOA lifespan to 2015. AGOA 1V came to be included in the improvement clauses as Africa Investment Incentive ACT 2006 allowing export of textiles under AGOA for five years 2007-2012 and extending the tenor of AGOA span till September 2015, (trade.gov/agoa/legislation/index.asp). The President of United States reviews on an annual basis the various participating countries eligibility status in the implementation of AGOA provisions for appropriate sanctions against non-compliant countries such as the Central African Republic and Eritrea in January 2004.

2.2 Operationalisation of AGOA

The general impression created at the onset of AGOA was that it was meant to boost the economies of the countries of Sub Saharan Africa through the improvements in their exports to the United States of America, particularly with waivers in tariffs, taxes and quota limitations. The focus was on agricultural products that meet the United States quality standards as prescribed by the international sanitary and phytosanitary standards. Special processing factors including equipment and manpower are required to attain such standards. The United States agency provides beneficiary countries with limited assistance by training in order to achieve the U.S and international sanitary and phytosanitary standards to foster increased export with improved knowledge of domestic and foreign markets. The agency currently, has 10 officers in Nigeria (WATA, 2012). The effort of the U.S foreign agricultural service may not have yielded the desired boost in exports to the United States market as many countries have not found the solutions to the quality problem which has posed a major barrier to exporters.

2.3 Product Standardization Requirements under AGOA

The trade liberalization and open market offered by the US under the AGOA act, have a minimum sanitary and phytosanitary standards, especially for agricultural produce and products important for maintaining good food quality and protecting human, plant and animal health. The environmental implications associated with the production of agricultural products entails that societal marketing and the concept of consumerism as advocated by John Kennedy in 1962, has far reaching implications to reducing the opportunities offered by AGOA in Nigeria agricultural produce export to the United State market (Ferrel, 2005). IFATPCP (2009) notes that the sanitary and phytosanitary standards posed additional demands on exporters and can limit market access for eligible products into the United States under AGOA. The United States department of agriculture (USDA) provides trade capacity and technical assistance to AGOA countries through its foreign agricultural services (FAS). The quality and quantity of internationally certified sanitary and phytosanitary food globally are in short supply because of the intermittent outbreak of flu and diseases especially the current Ebola status of West African countries where Nigeria was a victim (WHO, 2014). This goes a long way to tell on the human check done at notable international air ports in the world, less cannot be said of product which is host to some of the deadly diseases. The need for quality farm produce/product cannot be underestimated both at home and international market where these products are required. Currently Nigeria is not ranked among the first ten countries exporting its agricultural products to the United States market under AGOA (Opoku and Akorli, 2009). There are reasons for weakness in Nigeria exporting including the fear of failure, as it had been exposed that “Nigerian exporters had attempted exporting agro based produce to America but have suffered huge losses because of Standardization, for example in Gari (Cassava) Senile is considered exceptionally high and Yam is not up to standard and a lot of losses are incurred,” (Ayede, 2014). agoa.info/article/5498-agoa-forum).

The duty free and quota free products which countries in SSA are eligible for free access to US market were approximated to 7000 tariff lines inclusive of GSP and AGOA and all countries of SSA have more than 97.5% access to all tariff lines, though there are 316 dutiable tariff lines at present out of over 10700. The majority of the remaining lines cover agriculture and textile products many of which historically have been the most import sensitive, (Froman, 2014; (www.ustr.gov/about-us/press-office)). The exportable products covered by these tariff lines are categorized into six (6) major sectors including: Cashew; Shea; home décor and fashion accessories; apparel; specialized foods, (Bank of Industry AGOA resource centre-<http://boinigeria.com/>) There are also other products as chemicals, minerals, and building stone, Jewellery, Carpets, agricultural and fishery products, though GSP excludes textiles, apparel, watches, footwear, handbags and luggage products (www.ustr.gov/trade-topics/trade-development/).

Apparel generally includes craftsmanship, tailoring, embroidery, knitting, and other special skills required for the industry and Nigeria is virtually at zero level in this aspect of product export. The textile and apparel exports to U.S. market from countries like Mauritius, Lesotho, Switzerland and Kenya stood at \$850 in 2014. The U.S small supplier of textile and apparel were Botswana (\$15.5million), Malawi (\$13.5million), Ethiopia (\$10.0million) South Africa (\$6.1million) Tanzania (\$5.2million) and Ghana (\$1.3million) (Freund, Kimberlie, and Lerg, 2009). The production of apparel and textile products in Nigeria may have to adopt the Asian model as the development of apparel manufacturing capabilities is due in part to unique financial structure and vertical integration within family owned conglomerates. As further noted by Scheller et al., (2002) Asian producers aggressively develop their full package capabilities by adopting pre-production technology and taking the product from design concept to shelf ready. Nigeria has strong base textile manufacturers supported by cotton growing capacity and has no apparel manufacturing capability for export but has export processing zone. In Nigeria Fabrics is purchased and sewn at home or taken to a tailor in the local market who then sews custom apparel standard. The general notion is that the fabrics in these types of prints have little or no value appropriate for US apparel market, (Scheller, et al., 2002). Export constraints abound in loss of export capacity, high exchange rates, energy infrastructure, taxes, corruption and high labour wage and low infrastructure.

The following tables further demonstrate products space metrics under AGOA.

Table 1 Nigeria: potentially competitive products based on product space metric under AGOA in 2012

Density ranking	Product	Nigeria exports, 2012	Nigeria % Contribution	All AGOA country exports, 2012b
		Actual \$		Actual \$
1	Tanned Sheep Hides	51,349,094	41.7136%	123,099,238
2	Cocoa Paste	42,776,169	3.4874%	1,226,596,440
3	Wood Carpentry	2,403	0.0005%	489,270,037
4	Shaped Wood	236,961	0.7263%	32,624,726
5	Cassava	1,053,930	2.9100%	36,217,158
6	Building Stone	402	0.0017%	24,243,031
7	Cocoa Powder	674,136	0.2249%	299,751,380
8	Dried Legumes	3,023,053	0.8355%	361,812,983
9	Ground Nuts	278,908	0.3862%	72,215,152
10	Grapes	18,314	0.0025%	747,028,881
11	Raw Tobacco	3,899	0.0003%	1,507,457,515

Source: Growth Lab, Harvard CID, and The Observatory (product space/density data, including HTS,

Accessed December 19, 2013 GTIS (export data), accessed January 15, 2014.

The table above shows a steady less than 1 percent contribution to the total all AGOA country exports in 2012. With the exception of tanned sheep hides with 41.713%, cocoa paste 3.4% and cassava 2.9% respectively to the total all country export in 2012.

Table 2 Nigeria: potentially competitive products based on product space metric under AGOA in 2012

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2.4 Agricultural Production under Integrated Farming System as AGOA Optimization Strategy

Production is systematic in nature and involves a long term investment with a huge capital outlay that meaningful production of agricultural products may not be feasible if not treated as a system, and meeting AGOA requirements could be difficult before the end of the window opportunity in 2015. The availability of technology is required to increase agricultural output in order to take advantage of AGOA after meeting domestic needs, (Akanji, 2007). In context “Nigeria has good soil but no expertise in agriculture, the equipment and the laboratories to test the products to attain international standard” (Ayede 2014). Over 2 billion people of SSA are supported by an agricultural system characterized by modern technologies brought about by the green revolution. The integrated farming should include good soils, reliable access to water, accessible to road, markets, supplies of farm inputs, technical support from local and international agencies all required for improving the quality of products to meet the international market requirement (Pretty, 1995) but Nigeria is yet to attain this standard for optimized AGOA export. The integrated farming system will give empowerment to farmers who may be economically “poor” but are rich in knowledge of local resources (Rodríguez, 1997).

2.4.1 Songhai Farm Experiment

The Songhai farm in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State represents a model of crop production, animal husbandry and aquaculture. The farm was originated from Benin Republic in West Africa. The model was introduced into Abi in 2012 and has begun in earnest (Adegbalola, 2002). The production of crops and animal is organically and easily grown. The model is based on input and use of local resources, which is accessible to the poor. It is based on no soil degradation, no pesticides, no pollution and

no waste principle and practice (Adegbalola, 2002b). Waste from one component becomes an input for another component. There is a dependent relationship existing among various components of the farm for input resources of production. The integrated farming system under Songhai has the potential of incorporating the poor farmers, school dropouts, men and women and the rich in the society. The problem of export of agricultural products can be reduced through this farm project, for example beans exports to the United States under AGOA are expected to increase once phytosanitary standard is met (Michael and Didier 2002). The promotion of Songhai farm should not be limited to domestic interests but to ensure that export oriented training is maximized in order to actualize the potential of the farm to fill the gap in the export market of agricultural products.

2.5 Market Structure

Africa has remained a minimal force in the global context of a business with a share of international trade of 3.2% in 2008 (UNECA 2010). This was barely enough to support any export especially with low diversification of products from manufacturing and agriculture. The need to study the market and establish the structure is important, for example, in USA about “68% of apparel is sold by the top 5 retailers, another 30% sold by the next 24 largest retailers thus, nearly 95% of apparel sold in United States are by 29 retailer (Scheller et al., 2002). In the same vein, foreign investors in apparel seek countries with shorter shipping times, low political risks, favourable currency exchange high labour productivity and low cost structures. The ownership of business ranges from contracting per order, joint ventures and wholly owned and off shore subsidiaries,” (Scheller et al., 2002). The market may seem to be lucrative but AGOA opportunities are limited by quality standard of sanitary and phytosanitary requirements, quota, eligibility clause and capacity underutilization especially in agricultural and manufacturing with weak infrastructure. There seem to be little or no survey of US markets to actually determine the needs of the market as no links is firmly established between the exporters, local garment and textile manufacturers. Products are virtually nonexistent in relation to demand and the method of entering into United States market through contractual arrangements; use of Nigerian distributors in United States and the local market are not coordinated through an organized system. The greatest potential to organised market in Nigeria for Apparel export is Aba where there are adequate local artisans highly skilled for the production of exportable apparel products.

2.6 Marketing Information and Promotion of AGOA in Nigeria Agricultural Sector.

Marketing information is the systematic design that involves the generation of data/information about a particular business at regular interval on the sector activities through marketing research, internal records, marketing intelligence and decision support system (Vencil, 2003). The agricultural sectors have key players in different division of production; crop production, animal husbandry and aquaculture etc. These areas require peculiar information for the production which could be regarded as the downstream and the upstream phases. Both phases require basic information needed for production and sales especially in the foreign market of the United States of America under AGOA. Export potential areas under AGOA in the area of agricultural produce or products need to be identified; especially those listed in the generalized system preferences (GPS). Most of the countries among the top ten exporting mainly agricultural products have formed a market niche for themselves including Kenya, Malawi, Mauritius and South Africa.

The greatest hindrance to successful exporting is the lack of documents on general rules and regulations guiding the product movements as required by the Customs Regulation in this case the United States Service Regulations, or Importing into the United States. In all ramifications many Nigerian exporters seem to be ignorant of the existing publications guiding export of products to United States especially in agricultural products. The need to use attorneys or consultants who specializes in Customs matters is important. There are value publications such as Customs valuation title of the Trade Agreement Act (Section 2 of the Tariff Act of 1950 as amended by the TAA of 1979 (19 USC section 140 1a), the Informed Compliance Publications, AGOA Certificate of Origin Instructions Books 1-17, AGOA Textile Certificate of Origin, What every Member of the Trade Community should know about AGOA by US Department of Home Security Revised Aug 2003 are among the various relevant documents of monumental volume available to the SSA countries exporters at the Office of Textile and Apparel (OTEXA), (otexa.ita.doc.gov/AGOACBTPA/icp065.pdf).

The information on other producer's capacity in line with where they have comparative advantage is very crucial; this may as well point to the direction of where Nigeria producers should concentrate and learn from the market development. Marketing research most importantly has the capacity to generate such information that would form the bases of managerial and marketing decision making. The market potential of most of the agricultural products may vary within seasons but most fruits and vegetables are now planted and consumed all year round. Market price intelligence in international market of agricultural products is essential in respect to the change in foreign exchange rate. These rates are the market prices for which the international market buys and sell various agricultural products. The knowledge of these markets prices and their changes where necessary is an invaluable asset of motivation in agricultural production in taking advantage of the Africa growth and opportunity act. Basic information is needed in the distribution of human race in the United States of America, major agricultural products are widely accepted in the US districts of Washington, New York and other cities dominated by blacks, even the number of Black Africa in the US present huge market potential for Nigeria agricultural products abroad (Austin,2001).International buyers for agricultural product buys in form of forward buying; especially product like tea and coffee with export potential in Nigeria under AGOA. Forward buying entail that crops are priced and paid in advance of planting and harvesting. Prices are negotiated in advance (Umeh and Ude-manta,2002).

The provisions for marketing apparel and textile products under AGOA were listed as “the apparel articles assembled in one or more beneficiary Sub-Saharan Africa and from fabrics or yarns wholly formed and cut in the USA and classified under heading 5602 or 5603; - the apparel articles cut in one or more beneficiary SSA countries and yarns wholly formed in the United States if such articles are assembled in one or more SSA with thread from the USA; apparel articles wholly assembled in SSA from Fabric wholly formed in one or more of the SSA from Yarn from the USA or SSA countries. The shipments to USA have original visa on invoice and USA customs are to visit factories, producers, exporters for verification purpose with monthly export data to allow for reconciliation with US import statistics”, (Brenton and Ikezuki 2004).

The institutional requirements for the successful export of products under AGOA have been underdeveloped and not exposed to the public for utilization. The promotional strategies adopted are not clearly defined. The Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) had identified some strategic institutions that could provide promotional facilities for AGOA, including the work of the National Supplementation and Advisory Committee that could develop export plan for Nigeria, work with consultant Manchester Trade Limited to evolve strategic export plan, conduct market surveys to develop product profiles, organize workshop for awareness, capacity building, establish TIFA council and Joint Economic Committee (JEPC). There are also the trade missions to countries, product adaptation measures to improve made in Nigeria products through NAFDAC, SON, and FIIRO. Introduction of mandatory conformity assessment and 1509000 management system has improved made in Nigeria products quality, production of an export manual by the NCS to ensure compliance and increase AGOA Benefits. Collaboration with WTO to introduce standards and Trade Development Facility (STDD) for some selected products e.g. Shea butter and sesame, (www.nepc.gov.ng/images/AGOAA)

2.7 Marketing Communication Strategy under AGOA in Nigeria

The policies on AGOA in Nigeria and the origin of the act may be regarded by most established farmers as new or even unknown to larger number of farmers or agricultural producers in Nigeria. A cross section of both the literate and the illiterate farmers may not be well informed about the AGOA act as communication has been nonexistence or at best minimal. Promotion is a means of packaging and disseminating a potentially commercial message to elicit the intended responses from consumers, (Okpara et al., 1999). The governments and other stakeholders in AGOA are expected to promote it to all classes of farmers in Nigeria through various communication media. The identification of the various groups of farm holders is important. The market segmentation analysis according to crop production specialty and production capacity remains a vital step towards designing a promotional campaign necessary to reach specific group of farmers with the required information. A pool of marketing communication variables may be adopted as a means for promoting AGOA to various stakeholders (Esu, 2002). The most suitable channel of communication that could be helpful in the rural areas is the use of Town criers and holding of town hall meetings with local

farmers for a change of attitude towards modern farming and production system including the use of integrated farming. The use of social marketing communication campaign to change the quality of life through economic fortunes of citizen should be encouraged (Andreasen, 1994).

3.1 Methodology

This study was carried out through the use of documentaries and reports on the AGOA implementation efforts by different stakeholders and groups including government agencies, individuals, and representatives of United States government in Nigeria. In the essence therefore, literature review was highly relied on with internet searches and sparingly use of interviews of officials of Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC), Ministry of Trade and Commerce and Implementation and Monitoring Group on AGOA. The reports were analyzed and findings largely drawn from the available evidence from the literature and intuitive judgments.

4.0 Discussion of Findings

The product standardization of agricultural products to Nigeria optimization capacity of AGOA had shown that Nigeria lacked the capacity to achieve required products standards for the optimization of export under AGOA, particularly with agricultural and manufactured products. Nigeria had less than 1 percent of SSA countries total of non-energy exports and Sanitary and Phytosanitary standards were hardly met. The situation was compounded with poor safety of environment with recent Ebola virus problems and the products highly vulnerable to rejection as unsafe agricultural products. Nigeria was not ranked among the first ten countries exporting agricultural products to US under AGOA. The fear of product failure contributed to none or low export by Nigerian exporters. There was gross lack of adequate infrastructure to upgrade production standard of agricultural output as Cassava was found to contain high senile and Yam was completely not rated. Apparel and Textile export was nonexistent even when Nigeria was considered as strong textile base.

The impact of processing, packaging of agricultural products to the optimization of AGOA by Nigeria farmers had recorded low standards as the products exported to United States were poorly processed, packaged and transported under poor physical distribution conditions devoid of export requirements. The processing and packaging facilities were not adequate for the required sanitary and phytosanitary standards for export under AGOA.

The marketing information needs required to maximize export capacity of agricultural products in Nigeria under AGOA had no evidence of market intelligence through marketing research, poor internal records, price information and standard literature to support good decision making that could help Nigerian exporters. There were virtually no available records of export requirements on AGOA for local exporters and most often suffered great losses in an effort to blindly or ignorantly export products.

The effect of agricultural production under integrated farming system as a means of optimizing Nigeria AGOA export capacity was the low technology that hindered the successful implementation of integrated agricultural farms. Nigeria has good soil but no expertise to improve farming system including the poor or weak infrastructure with no reliable access to water, good road, supplies of farm implements, mechanized system of agriculture to enrich integrated farming system. The Songhai experiment is still undergoing trials and has not started yielding the results for optimized export under AGOA.

The marketing communication strategy adopted under AGOA was totally nonexistence or at best ineffective as promotions on the local and foreign markets was never record. There was no specific media attention or information dissemination through any local or foreign media specifically on Nigeria experience in the implementation of AGOA and towards changing the attitude of local farmers to accept integrated farming methods that may boost export.

5.0 Conclusion

The study focused on AGOA with emphasis on export of agricultural product optimization potential in the US market through professional marketing application. The study has influenced and motivated the need for

improved production capacity of Agricultural products in Nigeria to contribute substantially to the total regional contribution of products exported to the US market under AGOA. The right product needed to meet demand of the US market more importantly on the sanitary and phytosanitary standard required. The marketing implication of the AGOA Act can be applied to a conventional international trade export to major international market with huge market potential for agricultural products. The global market for agricultural product is enormous .However; Government still remains a key player in the optimization capacity of Nigeria export under AGOA.

6.0 Recommendation

The following recommendation is adduced to improve on the production capacity of Nigeria's contribution of agricultural products under AGOA.

1. The adaption of integrated farming system by all levels of farm holders, with emphasis on local input resources and technology. This effort should be supported by government at all level. The US foreign agricultural service representative should emphasis IFS
2. The marketing information need of the foreign market should be advocated by major stake holders in the AGOA programme. Specifically marketing research and intelligence is sure tool to address marketing information problem.
3. Marketing segmentation analysis on producers nationwide based on product and volume potential should be carried by various agricultural ministries.
4. AGOA programme should be repackaged and sold as a product to current and potential stakeholders through a well-designed marketing communication strategy by Nigerian Export Promotion Council(NEPC)
5. The programme should be extended for an additional ten years period. This is to allow countries have not really benefited to re-strategies to reap from the AGOA opportunity.
6. **Need for US established Laboratories in Nigeria**

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